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Research Article

**ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF PAST DENTURE EXPERIENCE
WITH THEIR COMPLETE DENTURES AND PATIENTS
SATISFACTIONS****Dr Ahmad Masoud¹, Dr Ahmad Sohail², Dr Bilawal Nawaz³**¹ BDS, Baqai Dental College, Karachi., ² BDS, Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences, Jamshoro Sindh., ³ BDS, Hamdard College of Medicine and Dentistry, Karachi**Article Received:** October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**ABSTRACT**

Aim: The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of past denture experience on patient satisfaction with a new complete denture using a self-assessment questionnaire.

Place and Duration: The study was conducted in Baqai Dental College, Karachi for two-years duration from May 2018 to May 2020.

Methods: Eighty patients with no history of dentures, who received new complete dentures, were selected for the study group. An equal numerical group of patients with previous prosthetic experience who had received new prostheses was selected as a control. The same clinical and laboratory procedures were used in both groups. Patients were asked to return one week after insertion to complete a self-assessment questionnaire assessing satisfaction with function, comfort and appearance. Patients in the study group were divided into three subgroups by age to investigate the effects of age and gender differentiation on satisfaction.

Results: Mean scores were significantly higher in patients with prior denture experience. Satisfaction was significantly greater in patients under 60 and over 69 years of age. The differences in the mean scores between the sexes were not statistically significant.

Conclusion: Prior experience with dentures was an important predictor of the success of full denture therapy and should therefore be taken into account in the evaluation. Patients aged 60-69 were the most difficult to satisfy. However, gender differentiation had little effect on patient satisfaction.

Keywords: past experience with prosthesis, satisfaction, complete prosthesis.

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INTRODUCTION:

One of the ultimate goals of prosthetic treatment is patient satisfaction; defined as "cognitive-based assessment of patients and feeling-based response to important aspects of the structure, process and outcomes of their services." It is a very complex phenomenon, influenced by many factors, often not closely related to the stomatognathic system [1-3. This includes not only the quality of the dentures and the condition of the oral cavity, but also patient-related factors such as attitude towards the prosthesis, personality and the interpersonal relationships between the patient and the dentist. Many of these factors have been investigated in separate studies with different results. Some researchers have found a significant link; others don't. Among the many factors related to patient satisfaction are prior experience with the prosthesis and age⁴⁻⁵. Experienced patients are reported to be generally more satisfied with their new dentures, provided the treatment has been carefully administered. On the other hand, it is assumed that as patients age, it becomes more difficult for them to adapt effectively. In addition, the literature mentions several diseases commonly associated with aging such as xerostomia, tissue fragility, muscle weakness, osteoporosis, bone resorption, arthritis, anxiety and depression as possible causes of prosthetic treatment failure⁶⁻⁷. These numerous aging problems have led to the conclusion that denture damage increases markedly with age. This prospective study examines the effect of previous prosthetic experiences on patient satisfaction with their new full prostheses in terms of function, comfort and appearance using a self-assessment questionnaire. He also analyzes the influence of age and gender on the patient's acceptance of a new prosthesis.

METHODOLOGY:

For the purpose of this research, eighty patients (53 males, 27 females with an age range of 36-83 years) who obtained new maxillary and mandibular complete dentures were included from Baqai Dental College, Karachi for two-years duration from May 2018 to May 2020. Selective criteria included no prior denture experience and the presence of adequate alveolar anatomy as assessed by the clinician. Criteria also included the absence of uncontrolled disease, diseases affecting the neuromuscular system, decreased salivation, and diseases strongly associated with emotional stress or disturbing mental health. Complete upper and lower dentures were constructed by the same clinician according to standard clinical and laboratory techniques. All dentures were made by the same technician in the same dental laboratory in the

institution. During insertion of the prosthesis, the oral cavity was checked for the fit of the margins and support surfaces of the prosthesis with a pressure-indicating paste and relieved as necessary. Using the same criteria, an equal numerical group of patients of the same age and sex, but with no previous history with one or more prostheses, was selected as a control group. The same clinical and laboratory procedures were performed as in the test group. All subjects were instructed to wear prostheses during waking hours and remove them before going to bed for the day. Oral hygiene instructions were provided. All patients were asked to return one week after insertion in order to complete Weinstein's self-assessment questionnaire⁷ and make any necessary adjustments. The questionnaire was translated into Urdu and its reliability and credibility were tested. The questionnaire assessed the patient's overall satisfaction considering 12 factors divided into three categories of function, comfort and appearance. The function category included questions related to drinking, chewing, biting and speaking. Comfort was assessed on the basis of questions concerning the tightness of the upper and lower denture, lack of gagging, and the comfort of the upper and lower denture while not eating. Appearance was judged on the shape and shade of the teeth and overall appearance. A five-point rating system was used (poor = 1 to excellent = 5). A total satisfaction score was calculated for each patient from a complete score of 60 (function = 20, comfort = 25, and appearance = 15). The patients in the study group were divided into three subgroups according to age (A: 70 years). Using the above-mentioned questionnaire, the influence of gender and age differentiation on patient satisfaction with their prostheses was assessed. Statistical significance analysis for overall satisfaction, function, comfort, and appearance was assessed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 17.0). The t-test was used to assess the significance of the impact of prior prosthetic experience and gender variability on patient satisfaction at $p < 0.05$, and one-way ANOVA was used to analyze the significance of age variation in the three age subgroups.

RESULTS:

The mean age of the patients in the study group was 66.2 ± 8.4 years (range 36-83 years) compared with 64.1 ± 7.4 years (range 45-77 years) in the control group. Both groups consisted of the same number of men and women (53 men, 27 women in each group), with a total of 106 men and 54 women participating in the study.

TABLE 1: SATISFACTION SCORES ACCORDING TO PREVIOUS DENTURE HISTORY

	Total score	Control Gpn=80		Study Gpn=80		Sig P \leq .05
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Total Satisfaction	60	58.54	2.111	54.24	5.328	.000
Function	20	19.30	1.436	17.23	2.546	.000
Drink liquids	5	4.94	.460	4.63	.769	.002
Chew food	5	4.65	.638	3.86	1.088	.000
Bite into food	5	4.80	.513	4.18	1.003	.000
Speak clearly	5	4.91	.363	4.56	.840	.001
Comfort	25	24.40	.836	22.56	2.396	.000
U denture tightness	5	4.88	.369	4.43	.925	.000
L denture tightness	5	4.58	.689	3.85	1.069	.000
Lack of gagging	5	5.00	.000	4.95	.219	.043
U denture comfort when not eating	5	4.99	.112	4.76	.534	.000
L denture comfort when not eating	5	4.98	.157	4.60	.773	.000
Appearance	15	14.84	.561	14.59	.959	.049
Shape of teeth	5	4.93	.265	4.79	.469	.024
Shade of teeth	5	4.98	.157	4.84	.434	.009
General appearance	5	4.94	.291	4.83	.471	.071

TABLE 2: SATISFACTION SCORES ACCORDING TO AGE VARIATION IN STUDY GROUP

	Total score	\leq 59 years		60-69 years		\geq 70 years		Sig P \leq .05
		n=19		n=36		n=25		
		mean 53.95		mean 63.9		mean 71.96		
		SD 4.49		SD 2.82		SD 2.19		
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Total Satisfaction	60	56.16	3.55	52.33	5.84	56	3.92	0.006
Function	20	18	2.02	16.28	2.86	18	1.87	0.009
Drink liquids	5	4.78	0.54	4.47	0.93	4.72	0.61	0.266
Chew food	5	4.21	0.97	3.5	1.09	4.12	1.01	0.023
Bite into food	5	4.26	1.04	4.06	1.08	4.28	0.84	0.634
Speak clearly	5	4.73	0.45	4.25	1.09	4.88	0.33	0.008
Comfort	25	23.15	1.8	21.67	2.68	23.4	1.87	0.008
U denture tightness	5	4.37	1.01	4.31	0.94	4.64	0.81	0.368
L denture tightness	5	4.16	0.83	3.5	1.19	4.12	0.88	0.028
Lack of gagging	5	4.95	0.23	4.92	0.28	5	0	0.348
U denture comfort when not eating	5	4.78	0.53	4.72	0.56	4.8	0.5	0.832
L denture comfort when not eating	5	4.89	0.46	4.22	0.97	4.84	0.37	0
Appearance	15	14.68	0.82	14.22	1.55	14.6	1.12	0.855
Shape of teeth	5	4.84	0.37	4.69	0.57	4.88	0.33	0.269
Shade of teeth	5	4.89	0.32	4.78	0.53	4.88	0.33	0.541
General appearance	5	4.95	0.23	4.75	0.55	4.84	0.47	0.334

Overall, the mean scores for patients in subgroups A and C were higher than for patients in subgroup B. When analyzing the results using one-way ANOVA, the differences in mean scores for overall satisfaction, function, and comfort between the three subgroups

were considered statistically significant. In particular, chewing, speaking, denture tightness, and denture comfort during non-eating were significantly improved in patients under 59 and over 70 years of age.

TABLE 3: SATISFACTION SCORES ACCORDING TO GENDER VARIATION IN STUDY GROUP
Gender Variation

	Total score	Male n=53		Female n=27		Sig P≤.05
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Total Satisfaction	60	54.58	5.329	53.56	5.359	.417
Function	20	17.43	2.515	16.81	2.602	.307
Drink liquids	5	4.58	.819	4.70	.669	.517
Chew food	5	3.94	1.082	3.70	1.103	.355
Bite into food	5	4.28	.984	3.96	1.091	.179
Speak clearly	5	4.62	.765	4.44	.974	.373
Comfort	25	22.83	2.146	22.04	2.794	.163
U denture tightness	5	4.49	.800	4.30	1.137	.378
L denture tightness	5	3.96	1.018	3.63	1.149	.190
Lack of gagging	5	4.96	.192	4.93	.267	.487
U denture comfort when not eating	5	4.85	.411	4.59	.694	.041
L denture comfort when not eating	5	4.60	.817	4.59	.694	.952
Appearance	15	14.53	.966	14.70	.953	.449
Shape of teeth	5	4.74	.524	4.89	.320	.169
Shade of teeth	5	4.79	.495	4.93	.267	.195
General appearance	5	4.79	.495	4.89	.424	.390

Table 3 compares the satisfaction results for men and women in the study group. As you can see, the mean scores for most of the factors tested were higher for men than for women, except for appearance. However, when using the t-test, the differences between the two genders were not statistically significant.

DISCUSSION:

Often, dentists and patients view the concept of success differently. Dentists believe that dentures are effective when they meet certain technical standards. Overall, your ability to adapt to a new prosthesis and your prognosis will decline proportionally with your health. Some of the conditions that adversely affect a patient's satisfaction with their dentures include decreased salivation, Parkinson's disease, myasthenia gravis, bulbar palsy, and diseases that are strongly related to emotional stress or impair mental health. None of the patients in this study reported any of these conditions. In addition, while one would expect a positive relationship between oral health and the patient's assessment of the prosthesis, some

while patients judge them in terms of their personal satisfaction⁹⁻¹¹. However, assessing success in terms of patient satisfaction is critical to the outcome of treatment with full dentures. The Patient Self-Assessment Questionnaire gives patients the opportunity to be open and insightful and is therefore used in this study. Several factors can influence your satisfaction. They are related and often have a related effect. These include not only factors unique to dentures such as comfort, chewing ability, aesthetics and retention, but also patient factors.

researchers have reported a lack of it [12]. Nevertheless, all patients in this study had the correct ridge shape. After excluding prior denture experiences as a satisfaction factor in this study, patients 60 to 69 years of age were particularly dissatisfied with their denture, while overall satisfaction, function, and comfort improved significantly in those under the age of 60. These findings are in line with the results of previous studies. On the other hand, the same variables also improved in patients 70 years of age and older, which is not in line with the results of other studies [13-

14]. Although difficult to interpret, this may be due to the fact that most of the conditions that prevent patients from adapting were absent and the sample size may have been insufficient, which is a limitation of this study and may be recommended for future studies. Nevertheless, two groups of patients; people under the age of 60 and 70 or older seem to chew better and speak more clearly with dentures; moreover, they are more comfortable, especially thanks to the tightness and comfort of their lower prostheses. The influence of gender differentiation on patient satisfaction with the prosthesis was also examined. It found that men were generally more satisfied with their prostheses compared to women, with the exception of aesthetics where women scored better. While not statistically significant, this observation is inconsistent with previous research which shows that females are usually more critical about their appearance¹⁵. This may be related to the socioeconomic status of the patients involved, data not included in this study. This again constitutes a limitation of this study and should be taken into account in future studies.

CONCLUSIONS:

Experience in making full dentures is considered to be a predictor of the success of full dentures as overall satisfaction with function, comfort and appearance is significantly improved in patients receiving additional sets of full dentures. This should be taken into account when assessing and planning treatment. On the other hand, age has a significant influence on the overall satisfaction of patients with their new prostheses, as patients younger than 60 or older than 69 tend to be generally more satisfied with their prostheses. However, gender differentiation seems to have little impact on patient acceptance of new dentures, although women tend to be slightly more critical of their dentures compared to men, except for aesthetics.

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